

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE CURRENT ISSUES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION AT HIGHER SCHOOL

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Abstract

The article gives an analysis of the role of globalization and internationalization for the construction of a multicultural education system at the higher school; ranges of problems have been examined and the specific features of this field in modern education are shown.

Keywords: globalization, internationalization, higher education, multicultural education, system of education, integration.

Today it can be confidently stated that two trends have been identified in the world educational practice. On the one hand, the role of education in the life of peoples is steadily growing, on the other hand, there is a crisis in education and its structures. In a number of countries, there is a process of transition to a new type of education, designed under the influence of multicultural processes. In this regard, research is intensively developing, aimed at studying the foundations, patterns of functioning and development of a qualitatively new system - the system of multicultural education. Today, we are increasingly confronted with such concepts as "global market of educational services", "global universities", "multicultural education", "Europe of Universities", characterizing for us a qualitatively new process, indicated in the development of international relations, we are considering so far multicultural education as a priori, which should be accepted by all nations. At the same time, despite the processes of globalization, one way or another covering all spheres of society, not every country seeks to take an active position, to integrate into the world educational market. The question arises of what will happen to the system of higher education if the manifestation of the alienation of a number of countries in structuring the system of a new type of education - multicultural - is observed more and more. What are the main reasons for this lack of interest and what are the ways out of this situation? Indeed, speaking of globalization, one way or another, we mean a process that implies global changes and does not have a return to the past. The emergence of the term "globalization" is associated with the name of the American sociologist R. Robertson, in whose understanding it is the process of the ever-increasing impact of various factors of international significance (economic and political ties, cultural and information exchange) on social reality in individual countries [8]. He emphasized that one should not assume that "globalization is a kind of gigantization or a mixture of heterogeneous processes. Initially, this is an objective process that determines qualitative changes in the global space, an increase in the interconnectedness and uniqueness of individuals or civilizations as a whole. At the same time, the central idea underlying globalization is that many problems cannot be adequately assessed and studied at the level of the nation state, that is, at the level of an individual

country and its international relations with other countries. Instead, they need to be formulated in terms of global processes" [8]. Today, many researchers say that global forces (by which they mean global culture or various globalizing ideologies) are becoming so strong that the continued existence of individual nation-states is called into question. Others place great hopes on globalization, implying stable sustainable development, defining it as cooperation and subsuming various national ideas and systems under one structural entity. Despite the positive and negative sides of this process, it is worth noting that this process was obviously not reversible due to the observed tendencies of countries towards the formation of certain conglomerate formations (unions, international organizations). All this has led to lively debates about what globalization is, when it started, how it relates to other processes in public life, and most importantly, what are its immediate and long-term consequences. The understanding of not only its negative aspects, but also its positive ones depends on correctly placed accents in understanding the essence of this phenomenon. It is important to qualitatively evaluate the degree of penetration within which globalization acts as a creative process. However, it is worth noting that globalization has raised the problems of a national plan to the level of vital ones. After all, it largely affected the national and multicultural aspects of public life and determined the constant growth of the level of internationalization of society. Undoubtedly, as N. N. Ponarina rightly emphasizes, these two phenomena should be distinguished as complementary components of the modern integrated development of the world community, where globalization is the emergence of a hybrid world culture and a mixture of national traditions, and internationalization is the formation of national states-communities and their interaction with each other [6]. At the same time, the fact that education is not involved in the processes under consideration remains paradoxical; its closed nature is still observed. Only in the last decade has a system of globalization directions been built on state education systems (and even then, we are talking only about the highest level of education, that is, universities, institutes, academies, etc., where, unfortunately, it is worth noting, economic preparations are underway for significant resource), in other words, the construction of the

model "education as pre-actual problems of developing a system of multicultural education in higher education acceptance", aimed at achieving economic benefits in the market of international educational services. The emergence of a number of national systems on the world market has become possible due to the expansion of scientific knowledge and its acquisition of an interdisciplinary character. At the same time, one way or another, social ties are built between the participants in the interaction, and responsibility for the produced knowledge, created to solve various problems, increases to a certain extent. Undoubtedly, in the process of cognition, a person acquires knowledge known to science about the object under study and the metasystem, replenishing them with new discovered information. At the same time, the mechanisms of the psyche develop, the skills associated with scientific creativity are improved, and a serious contribution is made to the formation of the orientation of the individual and to all other areas of human education (V. I. Bogoslovsky, V. V. Laptev, S. A. Pisareva, A. P. Tryapitsyna). In this regard, the expansion of quality control systems over the generated knowledge implies an increase in contradictions between the diverse polar scientific visions of various countries. This, in turn, can affect the quality of the formed knowledge due to an unestablished system of relationships between participants in the process of multicultural interaction. The latter, in turn, determines the importance of expanding the processes of internationalization, developing new mechanisms of interaction, on the adequate implementation and application of which, in essence, the very model of the future system of national education depends, taking into account the degree of its integration with other educational systems. Internationalization determines the degree of convergence of national educational systems and the transformation of higher education into a global social system based on the unification of problems, goals, objectives, approaches and, ultimately, the universalization of the content of education. From this side, in many respects in education, globalization should be considered not as a process of universalization of knowledge based on a strong convergence of systems, but rather as a process of borrowing achievements. In this understanding, we are not talking about a single system of higher education, but about the harmonization of historically formed heterogeneous systems by creating common standards to facilitate interaction. After all, the globalization of education, reflected in the creation of a single educational space, is aimed not at creating contradictions in existing educational systems, but at coordinating their actions, at transforming, at updating them, without which their development and adaptation to changing environmental conditions is impossible. Obviously, for participation in this process, the comparability of educational systems according to certain developed criteria is necessary. The system is one of the most influential, life-supporting social institutions, which is organically connected with the fundamental foundations of the social structure [2]. Obviously, in the conditions of the 21st century, it must change significantly in accordance with the new chal-

lenges characterized by the development of multicultural relations, while a special role is assigned to higher education as a coordinating center that explores the problems of its creation in the context of growing multiculturalism and improvement. However, a number of problems that can be formulated as follows characterizes the current situation:

1. The presence of different interpretations in the definition of the system of multicultural education due to different levels of development of science.

2. Significant differentiation of the problem of development of the system of multicultural education in different countries. It is obvious that each country is interested in resolving this problem to a different extent, therefore one of the main difficulties is the mobilization of all countries in resolving this issue.

3. Insufficient level of integration of scientific knowledge between countries to develop a system of multicultural education.

4. Lack of a system of purposeful training of higher professional schools in the field of multicultural education. Judgments about what this system should be lose their meaning without identifying its main essential features, without an initial definition that can become the basis for subsequent concretization, clarification and deepening, without recognizing it as a complex and multi-level one, the effectiveness of which is determined by a number of factors, according to many researchers, whose classification can be based on the trends of modern development:

- Science in the information society, which determines approaches to the consideration of various national systems in order to construct a single multicultural education;

- University education on the territory of comparable countries, including training in the system of multicultural education, as well as analysis of readiness for the creation and further implementation of the system of multicultural education. The factors of the first group are due to the trends in the development of science in the modern world, which has become a universal means of solving urgent problems of mankind due to the fact that its development contributes to finding the most optimal approaches to the development of a multicultural education system, as well as its further development due to the continuity of its development. First of all, the essence of the changes taking place in modern science can be defined as a transition from the strategy of disciplinary development of scientific knowledge to problematic activity. This requires the deployment of interdisciplinary and integrated research conducted by means of several scientific disciplines, taking into account the specific pedagogical tools used in different countries, the specific combinations of which are determined by the nature of the problem, which is to develop a system of multicultural education. Proceeding from this, the following questions arise: whether the system of formation of interdisciplinary knowledge has been created; what are the mechanisms for implementing this system; how integrative fields are developed, what is the role of metaknowledge in the process of cognition. Obviously, these issues require immediate resolu-

tion: after all, it is the definition of the leading mechanisms of integration that will determine the possibility of creating a unified system of multicultural education. Understanding creation from the standpoint of an integrative approach, determined by the purpose and purpose of the educational process, determines the research position of universities in various countries towards its development, in line with which the following assessment of tasks is built: system model - joint determination of the mechanisms for its implementation within the educational process - determination of the foundations of its organization (V. I. Bogoslovsky). Following the scientist, we believe that it is worth highlighting as such foundations: the theory of system management, the theory of its organization, the definition of patterns of development; revealing the patterns of becoming a specialist capable of implementing and modernizing the created system. The listed foundations represent different levels of essential links in accordance with mono- and multi-level systems that determine the content and organization of the educational process. At the same time, it is obvious that after the organization in its development, the system of multicultural education obeys the laws of synergetics and, one way or another, goes through several stages. At the first stage, the pre-bifurcation period or the period of systemic stability, adaptive mechanisms for changing the intrasystemic order work, when organizational influences are stronger than self-organizational ones - it is perceived and the experience of its application is formed within the framework of the educational process at the university. The second period, the actual bifurcation period, or the period of systemic instability, is characterized by the fact that at the bifurcation point organizational forces are lost, suppressed by self-organizational ones. In other words, when trying to improve the system and change it, inconsistencies arise in the understanding of representatives of universities in different countries. The third period, post-bifurcation, or the period of the appearance of order, is determined by the presence of order, which is self-organizing in nature, arises as a result of the transition to a new attractive state. Achieving this level is possible as a result of the purposeful work of all universities of various countries involved in the process of reorganization. In the current conditions of the urgent need to create this system at all levels of the educational process, work on the implementation of interaction and relationships between researchers and teams of educational activities is of particular importance [2]. At the same time, the created interconnected chain of these processes of system development requires control at all stages. It allows you to identify these discrepancies as much as possible in the totality of assessments of inputs and outputs and determine ways out and improvements at each stage. Thus, the essence of the requirements for resolving this problem comes down to a deep rethinking of the essence of changes in the interaction of all subjects of the educational process (educational systems of different countries), to harmonization of positions, to the development of common for all educational approaches adopted by the scientific community today [2]. The factors of the second group are determined by the trends in

the integration of the development of university education, which includes the system of multicultural education. In connection with the entry of a number of countries into the Bologna process, it is necessary to achieve greater comparability, comparability of higher education, which requires continuous movement in order to be fully completed. In this regard, we highlight the criteria by which it is necessary to compare national systems, and identify the main problems:

1. Realization of the historical continuity of cultural values and spiritual ideals of generations, preservation, dissemination and development of national culture, fostering a careful attitude to the historical and cultural heritage of peoples. When solving this problem, it is necessary to determine the criteria for creating a unified system of values due to its individual vision in each country and the readiness of higher education to solve this problem.

2. Creation of conditions for the education of patriots of the country, citizens of a legal, democratic state, capable of socialization in a civil society, respecting the rights and freedoms of the individual, possessing high morality and showing national and religious tolerance, respect for the languages, traditions and culture of other peoples. In this regard, it is necessary to analyze the systems of patriotic education in each country, to identify common and distinctive features.

3. Formation of a respectful attitude towards world culture, towards others, fostering a sense of personal responsibility for the survival of mankind, for its safety and sustainable development. One way or another, in the direction of developing a system for the formation of multicultural relations between different societies, the question arises of creating a system of sustainable development and determining its main criteria.

4. Training of highly educated people and highly qualified specialists capable of professional growth and professional mobility in the context of informatization of society and the development of new scientific approaches. It is obvious that the orientation towards the tendencies of the old pedagogical science does not allow the creation of a new type of higher school - "multicultural".

5. As part of the formation of a holistic worldview and a modern scientific worldview, the possibilities for developing a culture of interethnic relations remain unanswered questions about the use of integration mechanisms in solving this problem in a comparable country.

6. Continuity and anticipatory nature of education throughout a person's life. The main problem that arises in this case is the organization of continuity in the implementation of multicultural education at all stages of the educational process. A significant number of questions that have arisen indicate the unresolved nature of a number of problems that hinder the process of creating a system of multicultural education: problems of an axiological nature (values external and internal, national and international), mental and scientific (correspondence of the system to new scientific approaches) and technological nature at all stages of education (creation pedagogical tools, taking into account the trends

of modern science). However, in the current situation, when multicultural education remains a “myth” for a number of countries, the questions of finding a single technological pedagogical toolkit, taking into account the trends of modern science and in accordance with the analysis of the values of each society, seem to be paramount. This should arouse the interest of countries in cooperation in order to achieve the goal, which is the development of a system of multicultural education.

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